

SND Policy for Persistent Identifiers on Datasets

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SND policy for persistent identifiers on datasets

It is essential that we can identify and cite data used in research in a simple and reliable manner.

Users¹ of SND's services should be able to trust the provenance and reliability of data objects.

Attaching a persistent identifier (PID) to data is also an important part of making data FAIR. Persistent identifiers on published data are a prerequisite for certification of digital data repositories and are often required by many scholarly journals and data discovery services.

This policy applies to the datasets² that are described and shared via SND's tool DORIS for publication on Researchdata.se. The policy was adopted by SND's Steering Committee on 26 May 2020, with revisions in 2021, 2024, and 2025. It is implemented on new catalogue entries and data descriptions as of 26 May 2020.

1. All datasets described in DORIS from 2020 onwards shall have received a persistent identifier. Exceptions can be made until 31 December 2026 for data descriptions in DORIS that link to resource collections (e.g., databases, catalogues, portals) containing several datasets.
2. A global PID service³ shall be used when assigning a persistent identifier. The identifier shall lead to a webpage,⁴ a so-called landing page, which shall contain information about provenance, version, accessibility, and possible limitations to use.
3. The metadata for a dataset shall include a suggested data citation.⁵ The suggested citation shall include a persistent identifier.
4. New or altered versions of datasets shall be assigned a new persistent identifier and older versions of these datasets shall be saved to enable the citation of specific versions. The new identifier must therefore contain a reference to the identifier of the previous version. Data should not be deleted. If a dataset is withdrawn or unpublished, its identifier must be retained and resolve to a landing page with information about the reason for the data withdrawal, as well as providing a link to the current version of the withdrawn dataset, if applicable.

¹ Here, "users" signifies both researchers who have created new data and reusers of existing data.

² Here, we use "dataset" to signify the file packages whose content is described and made searchable in the catalogue on Researchdata.se.

³ A global PID service is a service that is permanently accessible, even for computers (machine actionable), and which has a system for automated redirection to new landing pages when they are created. Some examples of PID services are DOI, Handle, ARK, PURL, URN, etc.

⁴ For datasets assigned a PID through DORIS, the landing page is the catalogue entry on Researchdata.se.

⁵ An example of a suggested citation: Name Surname. HEI, Institution (year). Dataset title. Swedish National Data Service. Version 1.0. <https://doi.org/10.5878/0000-0000>